

The Effect of Applying Mind Mapping Method in Writing Descriptive Text

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Abstract

Writing is one of the four aspects of language skills that a person must possess. By writing, someone can generate interesting ideas and then pour them into writing. The mind mapping method is applied to see how the method influences writing student description texts. This study aims to identify the effect of the mind mapping method on writing descriptive texts for students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan. The subjects are students of class XI for the 2020/2021 school year. This study uses a quantitative design. The instrument used by researchers is a test. The analysis technique used to measure student work is by using descriptive text rubrics. The implementation of learning to write descriptive text using the mind mapping method in class XI students is carried out effectively, smoothly, and thoroughly, which can be seen from the seriousness of the students in participating in learning. Previously students were bored, but when learning was done using the mind mapping method, students were enthusiastic and very creative in making mind maps and concentrated very much on writing a descriptive text. The mind mapping method has a positive influence on writing the descriptive text for class XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan. This can be seen in the learning outcomes that the scores of the results of writing the descriptive text of students using the mind mapping method have increased between the pre-test and post-test scores, the pre-test average score is 51,3 while the post-test average score is 90,6.

Keywords: *mind mapping method, writing descriptive text, mind-mapping application, the effect of mind mapping*

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1. Background

Writing is one of the four aspects of language skills that must be possessed by someone. By writing a person can produce interesting ideas and then put it into written form. Writing skills are very important to master especially for students. According to Abdurrahman et al (2000: 23), writing is a visual depiction of thoughts, feelings, and ideas by using the written language for communication purposes or conveys certain messages. Zainurrahman (2011:2) argues that writing practice is the main key in achieving success to achieve the title "Able to write well and correctly". According to Pranoto (2004: 9), writing means pouring thoughts

into a written form or telling something to others through writing. Writing can also be interpreted as an expression or expression of feelings as outlined in written form. In other words, through the writing process, we can communicate indirectly.

From some of the opinions above it can be concluded that writing is an activity that is often done by a person or students. Because by writing we can come up with new ideas and writing is also a process of our creativity in expressing ideas in our minds in written form. In writing, we need the practice to be able to write properly and correctly because by writing we can communicate with readers indirectly.

One of the writing skills that must be possessed by students is writing descriptive text, According to Suparno and Yunus (2006: 46) that a Description is a form of writing that depicts something following the actual situation so that readers can see, hear, smell and feel what is the writer described, this essay intends to convey a message about something with its nature and gestures to the reader. Kurniasari (2014: 141) explains that the description contains experiences that are depicted. The experience can be in the form of an object. When reading and listening, it's as if the reader or listener feels themselves like seeing, hearing, or touching. According to Sujanto (1998: 11), the description is a description of the reception that is considered by the five senses. We see, hear, smell, and feel through the means of the human senses, and with the five senses that can be lived by others.

Based on the understanding of the opinions of the experts above, the researcher concludes that the description text is a text that describes an object or event that is felt based on experience, what has been observed before, so that what the writer sees, hears, and feels the writer draws or convey in written form.

Observations that have been made directly at SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan by interviewing teachers and students at the school found problems that students still experience obstacles in using vocabulary in written language even though they claim to like writing (interviews with students) but they have not been able to write in English due to lack of vocabulary. Then in the learning process, the teacher uses the question and answer method and discussion (the results of the interview with the teacher). However, students still feel bored and less interested in how to teach teachers the results of interviews with students).

The problem that causes students to feel bored and not interested in how to teach teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Islands is because the delivery of material is too fast so students feel they have not fully understood the material presented (the results of the interview), there is no English language laboratory, and student attention who have not entirely paid attention to the teacher in delivering the material because they are bored with the way of teaching the teacher. This causes students to sometimes be less serious in accepting material. So, even the results achieved are not in line with expectations.

Students need encouragement to learn their learning material by using effective learning methods with the selection of appropriate methods. In addition to encouraging the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process can also function as an evaluation process to measure the achievement of student learning outcomes.

Students can express their thoughts in their way. The process of pouring thoughts becomes irregular or even faltered when students are stuck in a learning model that is less effective so that students' creativity does not emerge. The method of discussion and question and answer has not been able to increase the enthusiasm of students in learning, so the process of learning

and teaching in schools becomes less effective when it is not supported by the creativity of the teacher or students themselves.

Based on the problem above, then one alternative to improve students' writing text description skills is to use *Mind Mapping*. Because the *Mind Mapping* method has never been applied at the school and the *Mind Mapping* method is a creative note-taking method that makes it easy for us to memorize a lot of information. After finishing, the notes made form a pattern of ideas that are interconnected, with the main topic in the middle, while the subtopics and details become the branches.

According to Bonita (2011: 98), *Mind Mapping* is a way to develop thinking activities in all directions. Also, with *Mind Maps* can see things from various directions and can develop creative thinking, interesting, and easy to remember. According to Caroline Edward (2009: 64), *Mind Mapping* is the most effective and efficient way to enter, store, and extract data from or to the brain. This system works according to the natural workings of our brain, to optimize the full potential and capacity of the human brain. According to Bobby DePorter and Mike Hernacki (2003: 153), *Mind Mapping* is a note-taking technique that can map creative and effective thinking as well as integrate and develop the potential of the brain's work both in the right hemisphere or the left hemisphere contained in a person. The *Mind Mapping* method is a learning method developed by Tony Buzan in 1974.

Based on some of the opinions above it can be concluded that *Mind Mapping* is a method that is suitable for use in learning because the *Mind Mapping* method is a method that can develop students' way of thinking using the left brain and right brain naturally. The *Mind Mapping* method is also creative and effective.

The use of the *Mind Mapping* method can be used as one method that can optimize the ability to write student description texts. *Mind Mapping* is a visual learning pattern that can harmonize the learning process with the natural workings of the brain. In *Mind Mapping* the two sides of the brain function according to their respective portions. With a combination of colors, curved images, and branches, it will stimulate visually, so that the information obtained is easy to remember. Besides this method is also categorized as a creative learning technique because in making this *Mind Mapping* it takes the imagination of the maker.

In connection with the above, researchers are encouraged to research the effect of applying *Mind Mapping* methods in writing description texts for grade XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan because researchers want to find out how they influence the mind mapping method as a method in the English language learning in particular.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Writing Theories

2.1.1. Defining Writing

Writing skills are one of the productive and expressive language skills that are used to communicate indirectly and not face to face with other parties (Tarigan, 2008: 3). According to Hernowo writing is giving birth to feelings or thoughts with writing. Thus writing is a series of activities to express opinions, ideas, or ideas in the form of written language symbols so that they can be read by others (Hernowo, 2002: 116). Writing requires the complexity of activities to composing essays properly because they involve regular thinking and various requirements related to writing techniques. These requirements are: (1) the

existence of a unity of ideas; (2) use of clear sentences; (3) paragraphs are arranged well; (4) applying the correct spelling rules; (5) adequate vocabulary mastery. Based on the description above, it can be defined writing is a series of complex activity processes that require stages and pour it into written form so that the reader can understand the contents of the ideas conveyed.

2.1.2. *Elements of Writing*

Writing takes several elements that must be considered. According to The Liang Gie, the writing element consists of ideas, speech, order, and rides (The Liang Gie, 1992: 17).

- a. Idea
Topic in the form of opinions, experiences, or knowledge of a person. Ideas depend on a person's experience or knowledge.
- b. Speech
Is the expression of ideas that can be understood by readers. There are various kinds of utterances, including description, persuasion, narration, argumentation, and positioning.
- c. Order
Order is a rule that must be heeded when expressing ideas. Means writing is not just writing, must heed the rules in writing, for example, the use of proper spelling
- d. Ride
Rides are also often referred to as tools. Rides in the form of grammar, vocabulary, and rhetoric (the art of using language). For beginner writers, a vehicle is often a problem. They use vocabulary, grammar, and rhetoric that are still as simple and limited. To overcome this the author must enrich the unknown meaning. A writer must be diligent in writing and reading.

From the description above, it can be seen that the elements of writing consist of the expression of ideas, speech used by the writer in delivering his writing, the order in writing, and a vehicle in the form of vocabulary and grammar. Where to create good descriptive writing must include all of these elements.

2.1.3. *Benefits of Writing*

Writing is an activity that has many benefits that can be felt by the writer himself. According to Sabarti Akhadyah et.all (1994: 1-2), there are several benefits of writing, including:

- By writing can better recognize the potential that exists in itself related to the problem being written.
- Through writing, can develop various ideas that want to be expressed in writing.
- From writing, can broaden the ability of thinking ability, both in theoretical form and in applied thinking.
- Vague problems can be explained and confirmed through writing activities.
- Through writing, can judge their ideas objectively.
- By writing, can motivate yourself to study and read more actively. The author becomes the inventor or problem solver, not just being a bug of information from others.
- By writing you can get used to thinking and speaking in an orderly manner.

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that by writing, we can recognize the personal potential that exists in us. The author will understand to what extent knowledge is mastered on the topic to be written. To further solidify the results of his writings, the writer must be able to increase his understanding and knowledge of the topic to be written.

Writing simple essays is required to fulfill several basic requirements that are almost the same when we want to write complicated essays. Simple writing requires selecting topics, limiting them, developing ideas, presenting them in logically arranged paragraphs or sentences, and so on. However, the ability to write is not only owned by talented people. Writing skills can be possessed by all those who want to be serious in practicing and intend to express their ideas in written form.

2.2. Descriptive Text

The descriptive text is a discourse that describes or depicts something based on the impressions of the observations, experiences, and feelings of its author (Slamet, 2008:103). According to Keraf (1982:93), descriptive text is a form of writing that is related to the writer's attempt to give details of the object being discussed. In the descriptive, the writer moves his impressions, results, and observations, and feelings, reveals the nature and all details of the form that can be found on the object. In writing the descriptive text three principles must be considered, the three principles include:

- a. In writing descriptive text there must be a clear dominant impression. For example, to describe a dog, we need to choose and tell the reader whether the dog is threatening or a docile and pleasant animal. We must choose one of the dominant impressions, neither can. This dominant impression will guide us in choosing details and when arranged in sentences it will be clear to the reader.
- b. Writing descriptive text can be objective or can be subjective, giving the author a choice of words, word colors, and a fairly broad atmosphere. For example, the objective description text of a turtle will mention the facts of height, weight, color, and more. subjective description text still requires the objective critic, but it also emphasizes the author's feelings towards the turtle, and also the personal habits, such as the turtle is silent, always in the water (sea), cannot fight when on land.
- c. The purpose of writing description text is to engage the reader so that he can imagine something we describe. Therefore it is important to use specific and concrete details.

In addition to the principle of writing descriptive text, some things should be considered in writing descriptive text, namely the rules for writing descriptive text. These rules include:

- a. Writing descriptive text depends on concrete details that are captured by the five senses.
- b. The author must be careful in choosing details to support the main impression chosen. Or in other words, the author has the authority to get rid of details that are deemed incompatible with the main impression.
- c. The description text often depends on the emotion you want to show. Therefore verbs, adverbs for verbs, and adjectives can be used more to show emotion than nouns.
- d. Specifically for subjective descriptions, we must be sure that the chosen main impression makes the reader believe (a complex mental state concerning beliefs, feelings, values, and emotions).

Given the many things that need to be considered in writing description text, several strategies can be applied to create a good description text essay. These strategies include:

- a. Convey all the details, then the main impression is built according to these details.
- b. Make sure the details are by the main impression. For convenience, record what the five senses sensor on a piece of paper.
- c. Bring the reader in chronological order in space and time. For example, explain the sequence of train trips from one place to another, or explain the flow of the river from the spring to the household.
- d. Use the approach first, later, and now to show the process of change or improvement. For example, the state of the forest before it was cut down and the state of the forest now.
- e. Choose the right emotions and describe them. It might be more difficult to get started, but it will be meaningful when it reaches results. Improving the ability to write descriptive text means that we also sharpen the senses. The story told must be able to describe a clear situation. Through descriptive text, writers can transfer a picture of a living situation (for example, because it causes emotions) and clear.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the description text is a writing technique that describes an object of writing to the reader as if the reader is directly in front of the object by using certain principles. To make it easier to arrange, there are several strategies implemented in composing descriptive text. The main function of the description text is to make the reader see the goods or objects, or absorb the distinctive qualities of the items. The description text makes us see, that is, makes visualization of the object, or in other words, the description text focuses on the appearance of the goods. In the text description, we see the object arable in a living, concrete, and round.

The main purpose of writing a description is to make the reader aware of what life the writer absorbs through the senses, stimulate the reader's feelings about what they describe, and present quality of direct experience. The object that is described might be something that can be captured by our senses.

2.3. *Mind Mapping*

Mind Mapping is a creative note-taking method that makes it easy for us to remember lots of information. After completion, the notes made form a pattern of ideas that are interconnected, with the main topic in the middle, while subtopics and details become branches.

The *Mind Mapping* method was originally introduced by Tony Buzan in the 1970s. According to him, *Mind Mapping* is a system of storage, data retrieval, and extraordinary access to giant libraries, which exist in the amazing human brain (Buzan, 2009: 12). Mind mapping is the easiest way to put information into the brain and take information out of the brain. *Mind Mapping* is a creative, effective, and literally, literate way to "map" our thoughts.

Mind Mapping put forward by Buzan is based on the fact that the human brain consists of one million brain cells, equivalent to 167 times the number of humans on earth, the brain cells consist of several parts, there is a central part (nucleus) and there are several parts branches that spread out in all directions so that it looks like a tree that grows branches around it (Buzan, 2009: 30).

Mind Mapping is a technique for compiling notes to help students use their full potential for the brain. The trick, combining the left and right brain work. This method makes it easy to enter information into the brain and to retrieve information from the brain again. *Mind Mapping* is the best technique to help the brain think process regularly because it uses graphical techniques derived from human thought that are useful for providing universal keys to unlock the potential of the brain. (Prayudi, 2008). With the *Mind Mapping* method, students can improve memory by up to 78%.

From this description, *Mind Mapping* is a note-taking technique that develops a visual learning style. *Mind Maps* integrate and develop the potential of the brain's work contained in a person. With the involvement of the two hemispheres of the brain, it makes it easier for someone to organize and remember all forms of information, both in writing and verbally. The combination of colors, symbols, shapes, and so on makes it easy for the brain to absorb the information received.

Mind Maps created by students can vary every day. This is caused by the different emotions and feelings found in students every day. The pleasant atmosphere obtained by students when they are in the classroom during the learning process will affect the creation of mind maps. The task of the teacher in the learning process is to create an atmosphere that can support the conditions of student learning, especially in the process of making *Mind Mapping* (Sugiarto, 2004: 76).

2.3.1. Principles, Steps, and Use of Mind Mapping

Mind Mapping uses the technique of channeling ideas using free keywords, symbols, pictures, and describing them together by using tree techniques. This *Mind Mapping* is based on details and a *Mind Map* that is easy to remember because it follows the thought patterns of the brain.

All *Mind Maps* have in common. Everything uses color. Everything has a natural structure that radiates from the center. All of them use curved lines, symbols, words, and images following a series of Titans that are simple, basic, natural, and following the workings of the brain. With a *Mind Map*, a long list of information can be transferred into colorful, highly organized, and easy-to-remember diagrams that work in harmony with the brain's natural way of doing things. (Buzan, 2005: 6)

Rose and Malcolm add that this visual strategy has several characteristics, including the following:

- a. Remembering people through vision, remembering words by looking; it takes longer to remember the order or alphabetical order if not mentioned initially.
- b. If you give or receive an explanation of directions, prefer to use a map/picture.
- c. Creative activities: writing, drawing, painting designing.
- d. Have a good visual memory, which is when we remember when leaving something in the past few days. (Rose and Malcolm, 2006: 77)

According to Buzan, note-taking and mind grouping techniques designed to meet the needs of the whole brain must include not only words, numbers, sequences, and lines but also with colors, images, dimensions, symbols, that are *Mind Maps* or *Mind Mapping* (Buzan, 2003: 122).

Before making *Mind Mapping*, we need to prepare the ingredients, which are blank paper, colored pencils, pens, imagination, and our brain. Buzan (2008: 15) argues, there are seven steps in making *Mind Mapping*. The seven steps are as follows:

- a. Starting from the middle of a blank sheet of paper that is placed horizontally. Because if it starts from the middle, it frees the brain to spread in all directions and expresses itself more freely and naturally.
- b. Use images or photos for central. Because a picture or photo will have a thousand words that help the brain use the imagination it wants to convey. A central image will be more interesting, make the brain more focused, help the brain concentrate, and activate the brain.
- c. Use attractive colors. Because for the brain, colors are just as attractive as images. Color makes images livelier, adds energy to creative thinking, and is fun.
- d. Connect the main branches to the center image, and connect the second and third-level branches to the first and second levels, and so on. The brain has two or three or four things at a time. If connected branches will be easier to remember.
- e. Make a curved line, not a straight line. Because the line will bore the brain. Curved and organic branches such as tree trunks will be much more interesting.
- f. Use one keyword for each line. Because a single keyword will give more power and flexibility to the *Mind Map*.
- g. Using images. Because like a central picture, one picture contains a thousand words.

In learning Indonesian, students can use *Mind Mapping* as ideas in writing activities. In writing, *Mind Mapping* helps students organize information and expedite the flow of thoughts. *Mind Mapping* helps students overcome obstacles in writing. This method is considered good because it has several advantages. The advantages include:

- a. Can see the overall picture clearly
- b. Can see in detail without losing the common thread between topics
There is a grouping of information
- c. Attract the eye and not boring
- d. Make it easier for us to concentrate
- e. The manufacturing process is fun because it involves images, colors, and so on
- f. It's easy to remember because there are visual signs

From the explanation above, it can be concluded that the *Mind Mapping* method can make it easier for students to write writing especially essay descriptions.

2.4. Implementation of Mind Mapping in Writing Descriptive Text

Learning is a combination that is composed of covering human elements, materials, facilities, equipment, and procedures that affect each of the learning objectives. The intended learning goal is a change in behavior for the better. In other words, the learning process is a continuous process between learners and everything that supports the behavioral change. In a

continuous process that's the right method needed. What methods are used in learning, the main objective of which is clearly so that students are skilled in Language?

This *Mind Mapping* method is very suitable for use in learning to write descriptions. Because in *Mind Mapping* there are techniques or models that very clearly utilize words, impressions, numbers, logic, rhythm, color, and space skills. With *Mind Mapping* methods will certainly help students in optimizing the potential of both brains. Because of the extraordinary interaction between the two brains, it will trigger creativity that will give ease in the process of remembering and thinking. With students accustomed to optimizing both sides of their brains, an increase in several aspects will be achieved, namely concentration, creativity, memory, and understanding so that students can make appropriate quality decisions.

Some things are difficult in writing, namely choosing what to write, determining the theme, and how to begin. With *Mind Mapping*, a theme can be translated into several other themes so that it becomes a developer of ideas in writing. Furthermore, when compared to conventional methods that have been used for learning to write, *Mind Mapping* methods are much better because besides being fun, this method also involves both brains. This is different from the question and answer method and discussion which are usually still theoretical in nature which only optimizes the work of the left brain. Creativity and imagination do not develop well if they still use the question and answer method and the discussion. Therefore, *the Mind Mapping* method is good to be applied in learning to write a descriptive text.

Implementation of *the Mind Mapping* method is as follows, students and teachers choose the theme of the essay then write it on a blank sheet of paper. The writing of keywords from the selected ideas is accompanied by symbols or colored images. After students make plans in *Mind Maps*, then students are assigned to write descriptive text essays. If there are still ideas that appear in the middle of the writing activity, then it can be stated in any branches or branches in the *Mind Map* to further elaborate in a descriptive essay.

Application the *Mind Mapping* method is implemented as follows. Students observe media images or photos provided by the teacher, followed by writing keywords of the selected ideas accompanied by colored pictures or symbols. Then students write the development of the keywords in the branches that surround the center of the essay idea. After students make plans in the form of *Mind Maps*, new students are assigned to describe them in the form of descriptive essays. Ideas that arise amid writing activities, can be stated in any branches or branches in a *Mind Map* to further elaborate in a descriptive essay.

The following is an example of Mind Mapping in Figure 2.1: BEACH.

The beach is one of the places that I like when on vacation. The thing that makes me love the beach is the atmosphere there, especially in the afternoon. The afternoon scenery on the beach is very beautiful.

The crashing waves are combined with the setting sun. People laugh and play under the sunset. Grains of sand touches the feet slowly through the fingers when walking along the coastline.

Not only that, but the white clouds in the sky also contribute to the atmosphere on the beach more appealing. Birds chirping as if listening to the song. The breeze that caresses the hair adds coolness to the beach.

Not to mention the clear blue seawater that is swayed by the waves. Occasionally fish appear to swim when viewed from the cliff on the beach. This atmosphere is the most beautiful moment for all those who due to the expanse of sand, the splash of water, the song of birds, and the increasingly awesome waves.

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the nature of *Mind Mapping* is a method used in learning by using effective, creative, and imaginative techniques by projecting problems encountered in the form of branches of the mind so that it is easy to remember them.

The nature of the *Mind Mapping* method in this study is that in learning to write the descriptive text for grade XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tikep using the *Mind Mapping* method to develop ideas that will be expressed in essays.

2.5. Previous Relevant Studies

Mind Mapping method research has been carried out by previous researchers namely Pratama and Yuniar (2017). The title of the research is “*The influence of the use of Mind Mapping methods to improve the learning ability of reading comprehension in SMK grade XI*”. This research aims to help students brainstorm any topic and think creatively. The results showed that the *Mind Mapping* method could improve students' reading comprehension scores

through pre-test and post-test, the pre-test reading comprehension scores obtained from the samples had an average value of 59.12 with a standard deviation of 60.00 minimum score of 40.00 and a maximum score of 70.00 based on data, an average value of 59.12 indicates that students' reading comprehension is still relatively low. When compared based on KKM scores for English subjects in schools at 70.00. While the value of post-test reading comprehension obtained from the samples has an average of 70.76 with a standard deviation of 6.17; a median of 70.00; mode 70.00; a minimum score of 60.00 and a maximum score of 80.00. Based on the data above, the average value of 70.76 indicates that students' reading comprehension is sufficient. When compared based on the value of the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) for English subjects in schools of 70.00, the average value is already above the KKM even though the difference is very small. It appears that the value of students who are above the KKM of 15 people (60%) of the 25 students who were sampled. This condition is better compared to the results of students' pre-test reading comprehension.

Wijayanto (2015), conducted a study entitled *The Effectiveness of The Mind Mapping in the Learning of German Language Writing Skills for Grade X Students of SMA 1 Palangkaraya*. This research aims to find out (1) the difference in learning achievement of German writing skills in class X IBBU students of SMA Negeri 1 Palangka Raya between those taught using the *Mind Map* method and those taught using conventional methods, and (2) the effectiveness of applying the *Mind Map* method in learning German writing skills. This type of research is a Quasi-experiment, this research has been carried out pre-test and post-test in the class of the experimental class and the control class. The following are the results of the pretest and post-test. From the results of the experimental and control class pre-test above it can be seen the t-test of the experimental and control class pre-test with a t-count of 0.111 and a t-table of 2.021. Then it can be concluded t-count is smaller t-table which means it is not significant. From the results of the experimental and control class pre-test above it can be seen the t-test of the experimental and control class pre-test with a t-test of 3.725 and a t-table of 2.021. Then it can be concluded t-count is greater than the t-table which means that the data is significant and the hypothesis is accepted. The results of the research data indicate that the mean post-test German writing skills of the experimental class students were higher than the results of the post-test German writing skills of the control class students (35,143 > 32,318). From the mean data obtained, it can be seen that there are differences in the achievement of German writing skills in class X IBBU students at SMA Negeri 1 Palangka Raya between classes taught using the *Mind Map* method and those taught using conventional methods. This can be seen from the results of the hypothesis test that shows the value of the t-count is greater than the t-table at a significance level of 0.05. The results of the calculation of the final German writing skills (post-test) were 3,725 with a significance value of 0.005. This shows that t-count is greater than t-table (3.112 > 2.021) and when compared with a significance value of 0.003 is smaller than the significance value of 0.05 (0.003 < 0.05), so it can be concluded that there are significant differences German writing skills for class X IBBU students of SMA Negeri 1 Palangka Raya between classes taught using the *Mind Map* method and those taught using conventional methods.

Anton S. (2018). The study was conducted by making students as samples with the title of the influence of the application of problem-solving based on *Mind Mapping* learning to improve student learning outcomes in electric workshop subjects. Aim to determine the effect of the use of *Mind Mapping* learning media on student learning outcomes in electric workshop subjects. The study used two tests namely pre-test and post-test. Based on the results of the normality test, it was concluded that the data obtained normally distributed. Normality criteria: if $L_{max} \leq L_{table}$, then the data is normally distributed. It is known before the treatment (pretest) the value of $L_{max} = 0.211$ with a significant level $\alpha = 0.05$ and the area

of criticism in this test $DK = \{LIL > L0.05; 13-1\}$ from the Liliefors L table distribution table = 0.242. score $L_{max}0,211 < L_{table}0,242$ then H_0 is accepted, sample value before treatment (pretest) have a normal distribution. Whereas after treatment (posttest) the L_{max} value of 0.156 is known with a significant level $\alpha = 0.05$ and the area of criticism in this test is $DK = \{LIL > L0.05; 13-1\}$ of Liliefors L table distribution table = 0.242. Test normality after treatment (pretest) can know value $L_{max}0.156 < L_{table}0.2242$ then H_0 is accepted, sample value after treatment normally distributed [5]. The homogeneity test concluded that the data obtained by the data variant is homogeneous. Assessment criteria for F-count test F-table, then H_0 is accepted. Tests carried out with a significant level $\alpha = 0.05$ and the critical area in this test are F-table ($\alpha, v_1-13-1, v_2-13-1$), homogeneity test results show that $F\text{-count} = 2.407, F\text{-table} = 2.69 F\text{-count} \leq F\text{-table}$. Mean data variance before pretest treatment and data variance after posttest treatment are homogeneous [4]. Hypothesis testing in this study uses the t-test. testing criteria If $t\text{-count} < t\text{-table}$ then H_0 is accepted / H_a is rejected and if $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ then H_0 is rejected / H_a is accepted. Significant level of 5% with $df = (n-1)$ [1]. Hypothesis test results are presented in Table 3. Based on table 3 Hypothesis testing obtained $t\text{-count} = 24.74$ and $t\text{-table} = 1.78$ Because $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$. then H_a is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is an effect of the application of Problem Solving-based Mind Mapping learning media to improve student learning outcomes in the Electric Workshop course. This is evident in the learning outcomes of students of the Electric Workshop Health Safety Work (K3) material after learning to use Problem Solving-based Mind Mapping learning media is higher than before treatment, namely when students study with conventional methods/lectures and questions and answers and without the presence of media learning. Results of the study the value of before treatment (pretest) an average of 50 and the value after treatment (posttest) an average of 8.53, in this case, shows the achievement of success in this study in terms of cognitive can be seen there is an increase in the value of learning outcomes between before treatment (pretest)) and after treatment (posttest). Achievement of increasing learning outcomes after treatment (posttest) due to the existence of supporting facilities for the application of Mind Mapping learning media based on Problem Solving while learning before treatment (pretest) does not use instructional media and conventional learning methods/lectures. It can be seen the difference in learning outcomes of the average scores between the two groups before the treatment (pretest) and after the treatment (posttest) which scores higher learning outcomes due to the application of learning, media, and learning methods that make students more active and interactive when learning.

Samaela, Jamhari, and Kundera (2017) conducted a study under the title The Effect of Jigsaw II Cooperative Learning Models and Mind Mapping Techniques on Student Learning Outcomes in Class X of SMA Negeri 3Poso in Biology. With the aim of the research was aimed to describe the influence of Jigsaw II type as a cooperative learning model and mind mapping technique on the learning achievement for biology subject at grade X, and then to describe the influence of Jigsaw II type as cooperative learning model and mind mapping technique simultaneously on the learning achievement. The research was quantitative with a quasi-experiment design. The first hypothesis: The results of the t-test calculations for the first hypothesis are presented in Table 2. Based on the results of calculations with the SPSS program, the significance value for the test results $t = 3,208 > t\text{ table} = 1,993$ and $P = 0.003 < 0.05$ so that the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a model influence type Jigsaw II cooperative learning towards poso X class X SMAN student learning outcomes is accepted. Second Hypothesis: The results of the t-test calculation for the second hypothesis are presented in Table 3. Based on the results of the second hypothesis calculation using the SPSS program in Table 4.6, a significant value for the t-test results of 2,153 is greater than

the t table of 1,993 and $P = 0.038 < 0.05$, an alternative hypothesis which states that there is an influence of mind map techniques on the learning outcomes of Grade X students of Poso Public High School 3 in biology subjects. Third Hypothesis: The results of the calculation of the third hypothesis are presented in Table 4. Based on the results of the calculation of the third hypothesis with the SPSS program in Table 4.7, an F-count value of 2.514 was obtained, and a significance value of 0.011. Because the significance value is $0.011 < 0.05$, so the alternative hypothesis states that there is an influence of Jigsaw II type cooperative learning models and mind map techniques simultaneously on the learning outcomes of class X students in biology subjects at Poso High School 3 is accepted. Based on the results of the analysis and testing of the hypothesis above, it shows that the independent variable (learning model) influences the dependent variable (student learning outcomes). The Effect of Jigsaw II Cooperative Learning Models on Student Learning Outcomes. This study uses a Jigsaw II cooperative learning model. Jigsaw II is a learning model that can encourage students to think actively and creatively in the learning process. Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing shows that there is a significant influence between the type of Jigsaw II cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes, this can be seen from the results of the t-test in Table 4.5 which shows the acquisition of the t-value of $3,208 > t\text{-table } df = 74 = 1,993$ and $P = 0.003 < 0.05$. The data shows that there is a significant influence of Jigsaw II type cooperative learning models on student learning outcomes.

Safrudin (2015) conducted a study entitled the application of the Mind Mapping method with a specific approach to improving learning outcomes in introductory business economics subjects at SMK Negeri 1 Karanganyar in the 2014/2015 academic year. This study aims to improve the learning outcomes of students in class X marketing 2 of SMK Negeri 1 Karanganyar on introductory business economics subjects for the 2014/2015 school year through the application of mind mapping methods with a scientific approach. This type of research is classroom action research (CAR). This study was divided into 2 cycles, learning carried out in each cycle using the mind mapping method with the scientific approach. In the first cycle, the application of the Mind Mapping method with a scientific approach had achieved the indicators of research success that had been set at 75%. In cycle II the application of the Mind Mapping method with a scientific approach can also successfully achieve indicators of success and increase. So in the first cycle and second cycle, the research carried out was said to be successful because it had achieved an indicator of the success of 75%.

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

The method used in this research is quantitative. Quantitative research is a type of research that is systematic, structured, structured steadily from the beginning to the end of the research, and this study tends to use the analysis of statistical figures.

According to Kasiram (2008), quantitative research is a research method that uses the process of data in the form of numbers as a tool to analyze and conduct research studies, especially regarding what has been examined. According to Nana Sudjana and Ibrahim (2001) that quantitative research is research based on assumptions, then determined variables, and then analyzed using valid research methods, especially in quantitative research.

This research is a design correlation. Correlation is a type of research that aims to investigate the extent of the impact of variations in a factor related to other variations in one or more factors. Creswell (2008) argues that correlation research is research that provides an

opportunity to predict certain scores because of the existence of other scores and explains between variables. Based on this statement there are two keys in correlation research, namely relationships and predictions.

3.2. *Participants*

The population in this study was the XI grade students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Islands majoring in Nursing and Office Administration totaling 20 students. According to Sugiyono (2006: 130), the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. So in this study, researchers took samples from all students of class XI, amounting to 20 people. The sampling technique uses quota sampling, which is a technique to determine samples and populations that have certain criteria. Therefore, the number of samples determined is 100% of the population.

3.3. *Techniques of Data Collection and Data Analysis*

According to Sugiyono (2013: 224), data collection techniques are the most strategic step in research, because the main purpose of the research is to get data.

Data collection techniques are the most important rarity in research because the main purpose of the research is to obtain data. In this study, the data collection method used was a test.

A test is a series of questions or exercises and other tools used to measure the skills, intelligence knowledge, abilities, or talents possessed by an individual or group. In this study, the learning process was used to pretest and posttest.

In connection with the research techniques that have been determined, the analysis used is to use the description text rubric assessment.

Before presenting a rubric to assess the results of the description text, there is a small note about the assessment in the 2013 curriculum. That assessment is carried out by carrying out the sharing of functions. According to Brown (2004: 7) assessment must be able to function to (a) identify completeness of the skills achieved by students, (b) motivate student involvement in learning, (c) develop positive student attitudes, (d) give feedback to students, (e) determine the level of student achievement, and (f) evaluate the effectiveness of learning.

Descriptive Text Rubric

Criteria	Score
Title	4 = if there are 4 elements
• Reveal special objects	3 = if there are 3 elements
• Not a sentence	2 = if there are 2 elements
• Use uppercase and lowercase letters	1 = if there is 1 element
• Without a period	
Identification	4 = there are 4 elements / more
• There is an introduction to the object described	3 = there are 3 elements
• There is general information about the object	2 = there are 2 elements
• There are no sentence structure errors	1 = there is 1 element
• There are no punctuation errors	
Description	4 = there are 4 elements /

• There is a detailed physical description of the object	more 3 = there are 3 elements
• There are details of several parts of the object	2 = there are 2 elements
• There are no sentence structure errors	1 = there is 1 element
• Choice of fresh and varied vocabulary	
• There are no punctuation errors	
Closing	4 = there are 4 elements / more
• There are conclusions about the response to the object	3 = there are 3 elements
• There is an impression of what has been described	2 = there are 2 elements
• There is an impression of what has been described	1 = there is 1 element
• Choice of fresh and varied vocabulary	
• There are no punctuation errors	
Use of Language	4 = there are 4 elements / more
• There are concrete language details, form to describe as if the reader saw	3 = there are 3 elements
• There are concrete language details, form to describe as if the reader heard	2 = there are 2 elements
• There are concrete language details, form to describe as if the reader heard	1 = there is 1 element
• There are concrete language details, metaphor to describe as if the reader feels	
• There are details with concrete words	

Scoring:

4 = if there are all elements

3 = if there are 3 elements

2 = if there are 2 elements

1 = if there is 1 element

Final Score = (score obtained/maximum score)x 100

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Description of the study

Details of all the subjects that had been researched as follows:

Table 4.1

No.	Department	Male	Female	Total
1.	Office administration	2	7	9
2.	Health	-	6	6
TOTAL				15 Students

In the implementation of the research, there were three meetings. The activities can be seen in table 4.2:

Table 4.2

No	Meeting	Activity
1	The First Meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students write descriptive text and the students' writing is used as pre-test scores 2. Provide a little material about the description text
2	Second Meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide material on mind mapping and how to use the mind mapping method in writing descriptive text 2. Practice writing descriptive text using the mind mapping method
3	Third Meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write descriptive text using the mind mapping method and the students' writing results are used as post-test scores 2. Provide a final test in the form of a multiple-choice test of 20 numbers

The subject matter taught in this study is the material about writing descriptive texts and how to write descriptive texts using the mind mapping method. This research was conducted to determine the effect of applying the mind mapping method. To find out this, the researcher conducted two tests, namely a pre-test where students were asked to write a descriptive text with the object as a place, while the second post-test text was asked to write a descriptive text using the mind mapping method.

4.2. Finding

4.2.1. Pretest and Posttest Scores

After researching with 3 meetings. Then the results of the research can be seen in the table below:

Table 4. 3
Pre-test and post-test Value

No.	Student's Name	Pre-test	Post-test
1.	Hamdal Rusli	55	90
2.	Sugiyanto Mancari	50	90
3.	Nurdiyanti Basri	55	95
4.	Hapsari Malik	55	95
5.	Nurhayati N Upacara	50	90
6.	Wahyuni Jufri	65	95
7.	Sumarni Kapita	50	95
8.	Sumiyati Rusman	40	90

9.	Mirna Hamid	55	95
10.	Farida Edi	45	90
11.	Fiorela Auf	45	85
12.	Rivanti Safira M Rajab	60	90
13.	Haulia Sabila A Pasi	45	90
14.	Surniati Robo	45	85
15.	Ika Yustikasari	55	85
TOTAL		770	1360
HIGH SCORE		65	95
LOWEST SCORE		40	90
AVERAGE SCORE		51,3	90,6

The frequency distribution of the pre-test and post-test results before and after the treatment can be seen in the following table:

Table 4.4
The frequency of students' pre-test scores

Pre-test		Post-test	
Value	Frequency	Value	Frequency
65	1	95	5
60	1	90	7
55	4	85	3
50	4		
45	4		
40	1		
TOTAL	15	TOTAL	15

The results above can be seen that the highest pre-test score was 65 as many as 1 student and the lowest score was 40 as many as 1 student. While the highest post-test score was 95 as many as 5 students and the lowest score was 85 as many as 3 students.

The results of the pre-test and post-test of writing descriptive texts in class XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan using the *Mind Mapping* method can have a positive effect in improving students' writing of descriptive texts. This can be described more clearly in the following Histogram:

From the above comparison, the application of the *Mind Mapping* method has a very positive effect on the students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan in writing descriptive texts.

4.2.2. Final Test Result

This final test is conducted to measure students' understanding after receiving the lessons that have been given. Students are tested for their understanding of the descriptive text and *Mind Mapping* methods. The results of the students' final test scores can be seen in table 4.7:

Table 4.7
Students' multiple-choice test scores

No.	Student's Name	Score
1.	Hamdal Rusli	95
2.	Sugiyanto Mancari	90
3.	Nurdiyanti Basri	90
4.	Hapsari Malik	95
5.	Nurhayati N Upacara	95
6.	Wahyuni Jufri	90
7.	Sumarni Kapita	80
8.	Sumiyati Rusman	95
9.	Mirna Hamid	90
10.	Farida Edi	90
11.	Fiorela Auf	95
12.	Rivanti Safira M Rajab	90
13.	Haulia Sabila A Pasi	95
14.	Surniati Robo	95
15.	Ika Yustikasari	90
TOTAL		1375
HIGH SCORE		95
LOWEST SCORE		80
AVERAGE SCORE		91,6

The frequency distribution of students' final test results can be seen in the following table:

Table 4.8
The frequency of the final score (multiple choice)

Value	Frequency
95	7
90	7
80	1
Total	15

The results above can be seen that the highest score of the final test (multiple choice) is 95 as many as 7 students and the lowest score is 80 as many as 1 student.

4.3. Discussions

From the results of the above research, the mind mapping method has a very positive effect, because the mind mapping method is a creative note-taking method that helps students remember a lot of information. According to Buzan (2009: 12), Mind mapping is the easiest way to place information into the brain and take information out of the brain. Mind Mapping is a creative, effective way of taking notes, and literally “maps” our thoughts.

According to Bonita (2011: 98), mind mapping is a way to develop thinking activities in all directions. Also, with a mind map, you can see things from various directions and can develop creative, interesting, and memorable thinking.

According to Caroline Edward (2009: 64), Mind Mapping is the most effective and efficient way to enter, store, and remove data from or to the brain. This system works according to the natural way our brains work so that it can optimize all the potential and capacity of the human brain.

In writing a description text, students need a method that can optimize their way of thinking to create ideas for writing their description essay. The reason the researchers used the mind mapping method in writing descriptive texts was that the English teachers at Muhammadiyah vocational schools had never applied the mind mapping method. So that researchers use this method because this method can improve students' ability to write descriptive texts.

Research using the mind mapping method has also been conducted by Siti Heni Yuliani, Teguh Prasetyo, Annissa Mawardini with the title *The Effect Of Mind Mapping Method In Life Recycling In Fourth-Grade*. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the mind mapping method on the learning outcomes of fourth-grade students in science subjects. This quantitative research uses an experimental method with a Quasi-Experimental design. The data collection technique uses written test techniques, observation, and documentation. The analysis used is descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. The final result of this study, namely the t-test results, shows that the learning outcomes have a significantly smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This fact states that the application of the mind mapping method affects the learning outcomes of fourth-grade students in science subjects.

Apart from Siti Heni Yuliani, Teguh Prasetyo, Annissa Mawardini who has researched using the mind mapping method, there are also other researchers, namely Hadi Wahyanto. Hadi Wahyanto conducted research entitled "The Use Of The Mind Mapping Method For

Improving Learning Outcomes Of Chasis Lessons At Smk I Sedayu". The purpose of this study is this research generally aims to describe the learning process of the competence chassis maintaining/servicing transmission through the Mind Mapping learning method. Specifically, this study aims to improve the learning outcomes of class XI B students of the Light Vehicle Engineering Department at SMK 1 Sedayu and to find out how much the increase in student activity and student learning outcomes by implementing the learning process in the subject of competency chassis maintains the transmission of class XI B, Light Vehicle Engineering Department, SMK. 1 Sedayu through the Mind Mapping learning method. This research is a Classroom Action Research (PTK). The research instruments used were observation and measurement of learning outcomes tests. The final result of this study is an increase in the use of the mind mapping method which can be seen from the average value of each cycle. The average value of the first cycle was 44.45%, the second cycle was 61.11% and the third cycle was 75%.

So, there are similarities from previous researchers and researchers regarding the use of the mind mapping method, namely that they both experience an increase from students after using the mind mapping method.

The results studied by the researcher with the title "the effect of applying Mind Mapping method in writing descriptive text grade XI students at SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan have experienced an increase in writing descriptive texts, this increase can be seen from the results of the pre-test and post-test as well as the test. students' understanding of the learning material that the researcher has given when researching. The pre-test mean score was 51,3 while the post-test score was 90,6. And the final test score (student understanding test) is 91,6.

5. Conclusion

Based on the description of the results of the research and discussion in chapter IV, the effect of the application of the mind mapping method in writing descriptive texts for XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan, so that the study can be concluded that:

The implementation of learning to write descriptive text using the mind mapping method in class XI students of SMK Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan is carried out effectively, smoothly, and thoroughly as seen from the seriousness of students in participating in learning. Previously students were bored, when learning improvements were made using the mind mapping method, students felt enthusiastic and very creative in making mind mapping and were very concentrated in learning activities to write descriptive texts. Students' assumptions about the mind mapping method are fun methods so that students don't need a long time to describe an object.

The Mind Mapping method is very influential in writing descriptive text in English learning for class XI students of Muhammadiyah Tidore Kepulauan Vocational High School, this can be seen in the learning outcomes that the results of writing descriptive text using the mind mapping method have increased the average pre-test is 51,3 and the average post-test score is 90,6.

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